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A REVIEW AND UPDATE ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN DISPENSING AND ACCOUNTABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The medical industry nowadays is greatly impacted by technology, which also has an impact on pharmacies. One fundamental area of computer science that has influenced every field of science and technology, from basic engineering to pharmaceuticals, is artificial intelligence (AI). As a result, artificial intelligence (AI) is now being used in the healthcare industry, which includes pharmacies. The ability of machines to behave and perform like humans is referred to as artificial intelligence. It simulates human intelligence and facilitates more intelligent problem solving. The goal of this article's is to shed light on the significance of artificial intelligence technology and how it should be used responsibly when dispensing drugs. Over the last few years, there has been a noticeable increase in interest in the applications of AI technology for the analysis and interpretation of several significant pharmacy domains, including drug development, dosage form design, poly pharmacology, and hospital pharmacy. AI also will be used in the pharmaceutical industry to assist researchers in making decisions on new therapies for ailments and existing medications. It will also speed up the clinical trial process by identifying the appropriate individuals from a variety of data sources. When implementing AI in pharmacies, there are a number of benefits and drawbacks, thus it's critical to apply AI responsibly.

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INTRODUCTION

1)ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE^[1,2,4]

Artificial Intelligence technology is used in each step of the drug dispensing procedure and in accountability, which decreases the health hazards and also makes fast the process. In 1956, the term ‘Artificial intelligence’ was coined by American computer scientist, John McCarthy who is known as the father of Artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) can be characterized as the reception of calculations and programming to immediate human attention or awareness in the assessment of complicated clinical information. It is also called Machine intelligence¹ which helps in processing many data to generate intelligent and precise decisions.^[1,2,4]

1.1. Types of AI^[1,2]

- Machine learning¹: - Machine learning uses software applications to become highly accurate in predicting results. It is precision medicine that predicts treatment protocols and the treatment context.
- Deep learning¹: - includes a combination of separate layers of calculations along with combined signals. It has great potential for diagnostic uses, being able to accurately analyse images. It involves recognition, text analysis, translation, etc.
- Human-created algorithms^[2]

1.2. Classification^[6,7]

1.2.1. Classification based on their calibre

Artificial intelligence can be classified based on its calibre as follows

- Artificial Narrow Intelligence or Weak AI: It involves narrow ranged functions. Machines are not too intelligent as they seem smart.
- Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) or Strong AI: It involves the human level. It reduces human errors.
- Artificial Super Intelligence: It is having more ability than human.

Fig 1: Classification of AI.

1.2.2 Classification based on their presence^[7]

- Type 1 'REACTIVE MACHINE'**: It has no memory system. These machines can be stored data only for a limited period.
- Type 2 'LIMITED MEMORY SYSTEM'**: It has a limited memory system that can apply previous experiences to solving problems. This is capable of making the decision.
- Type 3 'THEORY OF MIND'**: It involves human thinking to make out decisions. Theory of mind AI should understand human emotions, people, and beliefs, and be able to interact with a human.
- Type 4 'SELF AWARENESS'**: It involves self-awareness. It does not exist in reality still and it is a hypothetical concept thus known as non-existing AI.

1.3 Advantages^[1,2,4]

- It enables automated and definite conformity
- Improved decision making
- Eradicate prescription errors
- Prediction of treatment results
- Prevent fraudulent billing
- Digital assistants
- **Multitasks:** Human beings can perform a single task at a time but machines are capable of performing multi-tasking jobs and can analyse more rapidly
- **Increased working efficiency and technological growth rate**
- **New invention**

1.4 Disadvantages^[1,7]

- **Increased unemployment:** Reduction in need for human intrusion causes downgrading of job opportunities.
- **Make humans lazy:** Humans don't need to memorize things to get jobs done.
- **High cost:** It requires plenty of resources and costs a huge amount of money.
- **No creativity:** It cannot be creative in its approach. It lacks a human touch

1.5 Risks and remedies

1.5.1) Risks

- **Injuries and error:** AI may get wrong and patient injury may result.
- **Privacy concerns:** The requirement of large data creates motivation for developers to gather information from numerous patients. A few patients might be worried that this assortment might disregard their security.
- **Data availability:** Switch insurance agencies, prompting information split in different frameworks and numerous arrangements build the risk of error.
- **Bias and inequality:** There are risks involving bias and inequality. AI systems learn from the data on which they are trained and can incorporate biases.

1.5.2) Remedies

- **Data generation and availability:** Few risks emerge from the trouble of gathering high-quality information in a way reliable with protecting patient privacy. This helps to ensure patient trust and support.
- **Quality oversight:** Oversight of AI-system quality will help assist the risk of patient injury.
- **Provider engagement and education:** This will be enabled to provide more customized and better consideration, liberated to spend more time interacting with patients as humans.

2) PHARMACY AUTOMATION

Pharmacy Automation is the electronic process of handling, distributing, sorting, packaging, and counting prescriptions. Drug store robotization includes the computerization of normal tasks and processes performed in a pharmacy.^[8,10,20]

2.1: Trends

- **Flexible configurations in a smaller footprint:** - Flexible configurations permit patient treatment regions to alter the dispensing cabinets without the expense of additional equipment and floor space.
- **Smarter drawers:** - The innovation permits the cabinet to contain huge, lockable boxes that fit in the cabinet drawers, which store the patient's home drugs.
- **Virtual control:** - The system sends its communications through a virtual web convention-based system, reports can be created and sent straightforwardly to nurse managers through email. This is a big improvement over the old style and saves a lot of actual space.
- **Better inventory management:** - The refill process additionally is decisively improved with smart innovation.
- **Charge capture accuracy:** - By incorporating computer innovations, like bar code scanners and touchscreens, computerized cupboards offer improved charge capture during medication. This permits billing to be captured more precisely.
- **Evolution of e-pharmacies:** - The integration of online pharmacies can provide with unprecedented growth opportunities.^[9]

2.2: Functions ^[13,19]

- Inventory management - helps to reduce costs and improve operational efficiency.
- Drug interaction and allergy checks- Pharmacy automated drug interaction screening system detects drug interaction by examination of medical profiles of patients thus keeps the patients safe.
- Tracking medical history- tracks a medication throughout the medical history of a patient and provides accurate dosage drugs to patients.
- Tracking and updating the patient database - Patient tracking is presented to help the patients with services from hospitals and in retrieving the medical records of patients. This is a system that is expandable, secure, cost-effective, and maintainable.
- Narcotic and controlled substance monitoring - need to be stored securely and should be monitored as they can be misused.
- Appointment reminders - Sends reminders of appointments to create connectivity and decrease chances of missed appointments.

2.3 Benefits and challenges

2.3.1 Benefits ^[12]

- Increased speed
- Improved Accuracy
- Better inventory
- Enhanced workflow
- Better patient experience

2.3.2 Challenges

- Lack of uniformity
- Staff may lack training on computerized programs
- Drug dispensing machines may be programmed incorrectly.

2.4 Future Aspects ^[4,11,15]

- **Self-serve pharmacies:** In the future, self-serve pharmacies are more likely to turn out to be considerably more mechanically progressed. This could seem as though patients are being given a medicine by their primary care physician, frequently with a QR code, and afterward taking this to a participating self-service pharmacy. .
- **Robotic pharmacy automation:** Automated medication dispensing system, automated packaging and labelling systems, automated medication compounding system, storage retrieval system, and tabletop counters.
- **Robotic automation in the production process:** Their machines can store the different medications, as well as dispense and distribute them to individual patients in emergency clinics. Mechanical robotization can help the medical framework by offering quality support in an exceptionally brief time.
- **Pharmacy automation in Research:** Researchers are developing smart mirrors that utilize advanced cameras and your breath to distinguish health variations. Smartphones are developing to allow them to act as point-of-care and home health diagnostic tools.

3) DRUG DISPENSING

Drug dispensing is one of the important elements of the rational use of medicine. The staff who dispense medicine should be trained and have the skill to dispense medicine precisely. Dispensing refers to the procedure of preparing and giving the medicinal drug to a named individual based on prescription ^[2,3,9]

3.1 Steps involved in Drug dispensing ^[2,17]

Fig 2: steps involved in drug dispensing.

3.2 Errors in Drug dispensing^[4,5,8]

A dispensing error is the disparity between the composed order in a medical prescription and the following of this order.⁸ These errors are made by the pharmacy staff when dispensing to the hospital. Dispensing is an integral part of the quality utilization of the medication and together with patient counselling, forms the center professional activities of a pharmacist. Inappropriate packaging

- **Inappropriate packaging**
- **Poor labelling**
- **Lack of right information**
- **Over workload**

3.3 AI in drug dispensing^[1, 6]

Dispensing of drugs is the systematic way of preparing and dispensing medicines to a specific individual based on prescription^[1].

- **Dispensing Robots:** They are used to maximize efficiency and accuracy through automation that reduces errors and saves time.
- **Prescription Reordering Apps:** It allows patients to reorder the repeated prescription through apps. Thus patients can check prescriptions.
- **Electronic CD Registers:** There will be a great reduction in errors by using CD Registers.
- **Prescription Collection Points:** Prescription collection points provide a collection of prescriptions at any time without queuing and it can save time.
- **Pharmacy Management Systems:** It is also known as a pharmacy information system. It is a system that stores information and organizes the medicine usage process^[6].

3.4 Future aspects

Technology and Automation in Pharmaceutical Care: In the future, technologies that dispense medications, manage patient information, and evaluate drug therapies will free pharmacists to give expanded patient consideration⁷. One of the biggest concerns, pharmacies at present have about robotized medication dispensation is the risk of cross-contamination. One machine processing many different medications needs to be cleaned between every activity. Automated dispensers can further stack the pills into conveyance drones for at-home conveyance. Such centres will act as a door to access advanced healthcare technologies conveniently. Drones have great potential in transporting drugs, immunization, or medical guidance at a faster rate. The medical drone company Zip line delivers medical supplies to hospitals through drones as a feature of the local healthcare system. By automating the whole fulfilment process, pharmacies are able to very quickly dispense the proper medicine to the right patient, with a much higher rate of accuracy.

4) AUTOMATED DISPENSING SYSTEM (ADS)^[21,22]

Automated dispensing is a pharmacy practice in which an equipment dispenses medications and fills prescriptions. Automated dispensing system (ADS) means a mechanical system that performs activities, other than compounding or administration, relative to the pharmacy services including storage, packaging, counting, labeling, and dispensing of medications and which collects, and monitors all transaction data.^{1,2,4}

Fig 1: Work process of Automated Dispensing System.

4.1 Advantages^[3]

- Staff satisfaction
- Enables pharmacists to save their work
- Provides fast and easy access
- Reducing incidents or errors
- Time saving
- Simplifying the process with greater productivity

4.2 Disadvantages^[3]

- **Incorrect programming:** If a pharmacist is in a hurry to give a patient the medication and programs the wrong dose into the computerized system.
- **Lack of physical evaluation:** Even if online evaluation is done, the physical evaluation should be done and the process is licensed by health care professionals.
- **Dispense without prescription:** Some online pharmacies can dispense medication to patients without requiring a prescription. This puts human health at risk and it is difficult to prevent this.

4.3 Manufacturers

4.5.1 Pyxis Corporation

Pyxis Corporation was a San Diego company co-founded by Ronald R. Taylor and investor Tim Wollaeger in 1987. Pyxis Corporation was the market leader for automated medication as the company was the first to develop MedStation products in 1990. They pierced the hospital market with their first generation Med Stations. Pyxis launched their Supply Station line to manage the medical supply chain in the mid-1990s. In 1996, Pyxis was procured via Cardinal Health. Their development proceeded, and they maintained between 60-70% of the market share for pharmacy dispensing systems that continues to now. In 2009, Cardinal veered off clinical and clinical item divisions, including Pyxi, to form CareFusion. Then, in October 2014, CareFusion was offered to Becton Dickinson. Regardless of the different buyouts, Pyxis has figured out how to keep the best position on the lookout.

4.5.2 Omnicell

Omnicell is an American multinational healthcare technology company headquartered in California. It manufactures automated systems in hospitals and other healthcare settings. Its products are marketed under the brand names Omnicell and Enliven Health. Omnicell Technologies, Inc. was established by Randall ALipps in September 1992 after his child was hospitalized at birth and he noticed that medical attendants experienced difficulty in locating medical supplies. With the help of graduate students from Stanford University, he developed a prototype of a system that automated inventory management tasks performed manually by medical attendants. The Omni Supplier cabinet was the first line product launched.

4.5.3 AcuDose

AcuDose is the third biggest pharmacy automation product line and was procured by McKesson in 1998. They were initially framed as Automated Prescription Systems, Inc. of Pineville, La. In 2013, McKesson then offered the business to Aesynt. In 2016, they were sold again to Omnicell. Their dispensing units have been redesigned recently, and offer a feature that permits medical staff to hold their place in the workflow assuming that they get hindered and need to return later. When the user logs back in, the framework recollects where they left off. AcuDose also has the ROBOT-Rx central automated dispensing product.

Fig 4: Acu Dose.

4.5.4 Cerner RxStation

Cerner is one of the largest providers of enterprise EMR and clinical documentation software and the Rx Station system is a relative newcomer from Cerner. It was developed by a major medical records software vendor, built as an integrated solution on top of an existing product which sets it different from others. The Rx station allows pharmacists to maintain a drug formulary and a barcode throughout the medication process. Advanced reporting abilities may improve reconciliation and diminish drug redirection.

4.5.5 Capsa Healthcare

Capsa Healthcare offers hardware systems like computing carts, isolation medical carts, computer workstations, medication carts, and pharmacy automation systems, mobile point-of-care hospitals, LTC computing carts, a full line of medication storage carts and pharmacy pill and tablet counting fulfillment technology, point-of-care medical wall mount arms in the pharmacy automation industries and healthcare providers software to understand their challenges and offering high quality, integrated solutions for medication management.

One of their products is First Dose, which can be used to track who is getting the medication, what medication is pulled, and to whom the medication is for. Capsa Healthcare proposes to have the best security for managing controlled medications, STAT/first doses and e-kits.

Fig 5: Capsa Healthcare.

4.5.6 Full script

Full script is a software platform for dispensing proficient-grade nutraceuticals and supplements. It permits health practitioners to prescribe and dispense supplements from an index of health products from different brands. Also, it allows them to send personalized product recommendations directly by email or SMS to patients.

4.5.7 Med Avail

Med Avail Technologies provides a computerized kiosk for automated medication dispensing. The Med Avail Med Center, helps with dispensing prescription drugs and over-the-counter drugs. The company plans and makes pharmacist-controlled automated prescription medicine dispensing vaults. It is planned for organization in hospitals, pharmacies, medical clinics, and other locations. The company incorporates advanced robotics, two-way video teleconferencing, and a secure network for medical information of patients to create a prescription medication dispensing system.

4.5.8 Talyst

Talyst Company was founded in 2002 and provides Pharmacy Management solutions to pharmacies and hospitals and automated medication management systems to acute care hospital pharmacies. Talyst launched AutoPharmA, an innovative software platform designed to integrate medication storage, inventory, ordering, barcoding labelling, controlled substance monitoring and clinical systems, in 2003.

4.5.9 Asteres

Asteres provides pharmacy automation for the storage and delivery of prescriptions using secure self-service kiosks. They were one of the first companies to popularize a system to store and deliver finished prescriptions to consumers in retail pharmacies. This allows consumers to pick up and pay for their prescriptions at their convenience. Retailers can expand prescription pickup hours without adding staff.

5)ACCOUNTABILITY^[23, 24,25]

The term “accountability” within health care is having three components:

1. An individual’s professional accountability for the nature of their work.
2. The accountability of health professionals within the association.
3. Accountability with others for the association performance and for arrangement of Services.

5.1 Levels of accountability^[1]

- **Organizational level:** - department and individual levels should run.
- **Departmental level:** - the pharmacy department needs to be aligned with the organization’s goals.
- **Individual level:-** Individuals needs to be aligned with the organization’s goals.

5.2 Types of accountability^[3]

- **Financial accountability:** tracking and giving an account on allocation, payment and use of financial assets, utilizing the tools of auditing, budgeting and accounting. Health policymakers need the capacity to track and analyse drug costs different types of facilities to identify price variation
- **Performance accountability:** refers to exhibiting and accounting for performance in light of settled upon performance targets. At the health system level, the focus is on the services, results and programmes, not on individual assistance encounters between patients and suppliers.
- **Political accountability:** In political/democratic accountability ensures that government follows on electoral commitments, satisfies the public trust, aggregates and addresses citizens’ interests, and answers progressing and arising cultural requirements and concerns.
- **Professional accountability:** is basic to professional practice, and is fundamentally concerned with weighing up the interests of patients and clients.

5.3 Steps involved in accountability^[1]

Accountability is a commitment or willingness to accept liability or to account for your activities Pharmacists often council patients to be accountable for taking their medications consistently or in supporting them. Here are some steps involved to create accountability.

- Set expectations
- Invite commitment
- Measure progress
- Provide feedback
- Link to consequences
- Evaluate effectiveness

CONCLUSION

It is impossible for us to envision the future without "Artificial Intelligence" (AI). The benefits of AI have already been observed in the pharmaceutical sector. Pharmacy tasks are made simpler and treatment efficiency is increased by the automated dispensing system and other pharmacy automation technology. AI is playing a big part in managing and storing data. The methods involved in developing new drugs in healthcare are being revolutionized by AI and machine learning. When implementing AI in pharmacies, there are a number of benefits and drawbacks, Therefore, it is strongly recommended that pharmacists should acquire the relevant hard skills that promote AI augmentation. Pharmacists must also be allowed to develop an understanding of AI through continuing education, data science courses or pharmacy residencies with a focus on AI topics should be made available for pharmacists seeking more hands-on involvement in AI development, governance, and use.

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